

A New Forms of Feebly Generalized Closed Sets in Kasaj Topological Spaces

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to introduce an entirely new type of feebly generalized-pre-closed set and feebly generalized-semi-pre closed set in Kasaj topological spaces are called KS_{fgp} -closed set and KS_{fgsp} -closed set, and to investigate the relationships between this set and other sets in these spaces. Characteristics of KS_{fgp} -closed and KS_{fgsp} -closed sets are provided.

Keywords: $KS_R(X)$, KS-feebly closed sets, KS-feebly semi closed sets, KS-feebly pre closed sets, KS- α -closed sets, KS- β -closed sets, KS_{fg} -closed sets, KS_{fgp} -closed sets, KS_{fgsp} -closed sets.

1. Introduction

In 1970, Levine [4] introduced the concept of generalized closed sets in topological spaces. This was introduced as generalization of closed sets in topological space and new results were proved. Thivagar et al. [3] introduced Nano topological spaces with respect to a subset $\mathcal{X}$ of a universal set $\mathcal{U}$ which is defined in terms of lower and upper approximation of $\mathcal{X}$. Chandrashekar [1] introduced a new topology namely, Micro topology which is extension of nano topological space and we introduced partial extension of Micro topological space namely Kashyap G.Rachch and Sajeed topological spaces. Rachchh and Sajeed [6] introduced partial extension of Micro topological space namely .Rachchh and Sajeed topological spaces. Rachchh and Sajeed [7] introduced Kasaj generalized closed sets in Kasaj topological spaces. Sathishmohan et al. [5] introduced the concept of Kasaj generalized pre closed sets and Kasaj generalized semi pre closed sets in Kasaj topological spaces. In 1978, Maheshwari and Tapi [8] introduced the concept of feebly open sets and Ibraheem introduced the concept of feebly generalized closed sets in general topological spaces.

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In this paper, we shall define Kasaj feebly generalized pre closed sets and Kasaj feebly generalized semi pre closed sets in Kasaj topological spaces. In this paper we use the following symbols Kasaj Closed, Kasaj Feebly Closed, Kasaj Feebly Open, Kasaj Feebly Semi Closed, Kasaj Feebly Semi Open, Kasaj Feebly Pre Closed, Kasaj Feebly Pre Open, Kasaj Feebly α Closed, Kasaj Feebly β Closed, Kasaj Feebly Generalized Closed, Kasaj Generalized Pre Closed, Kasaj Generalized Semi Pre Closed, Kasaj topological spaces, KS_{fg} -interior of P, KS_{fgp} -interior of P, KS_{fgsp} -interior of P, KS_{fg} -neighbourhood, KS_{fgp} -neighbourhood, KS_{fgsp} -neighbourhood will be denoted as KS- $\mathfrak{C}$, KS- $\mathfrak{D}$, KS- $\mathfrak{F}$. $\mathfrak{C}$, KS- $\mathfrak{F}$. $\mathfrak{O}$, KS- $\mathfrak{F}$. $\mathfrak{S}$. $\mathfrak{C}$, KS- $\mathfrak{F}$. $\mathfrak{S}$. $\mathfrak{O}$, KS- $\mathfrak{F}$. $\mathfrak{P}$. $\mathfrak{C}$, KS- $\mathfrak{F}$. $\mathfrak{P}$. $\mathfrak{O}$, KS- $\mathfrak{F}$. α . $\mathfrak{C}$, KS- $\mathfrak{F}$. β . $\mathfrak{C}$, KS- $\mathfrak{F}$. $\mathfrak{S}$. $\mathfrak{C}$, KS- $\mathfrak{F}$. $\mathfrak{S}$. $\mathfrak{P}$. $\mathfrak{C}$, KS- $\mathfrak{F}$. $\mathfrak{S}$. $\mathfrak{S}$. $\mathfrak{P}$. $\mathfrak{C}$, $\mathfrak{K}$. $\mathfrak{T}$. $\mathfrak{S}$, KS_{fg} - $\mathfrak{J}$ ($\mathfrak{P}$), KS_{fgp} - $\mathfrak{J}$ ($\mathfrak{P}$), KS_{fgsp} - $\mathfrak{J}$ ($\mathfrak{P}$), KS_{fg} - $\mathfrak{N}$. $\mathfrak{B}$. $\mathfrak{D}$, KS_{fgp} - $\mathfrak{N}$. $\mathfrak{B}$. $\mathfrak{D}$, KS_{fgsp} - $\mathfrak{N}$. $\mathfrak{B}$. $\mathfrak{D}$ respectively.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [2] Let $\mathcal{U}$ be a non-empty Universal set and $\mathcal{R}$ be an equivalence relation on $\mathcal{U}$ and it is named as the indiscernibility relation. As $\mathcal{R}$ is an equivalence relation, we get disjoint partition and each equivalence with one another. The pair $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{R})$ is called as approximation space. Let $\mathcal{U}$ set of objects called the universe $\mathcal{R}$ be an equivalence relation on $\mathcal{U}$ named as the indiscernibility relation. Elements belonging to the same equivalence class are said to be indiscernible with one another. The pair $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{R})$ is said to be the approximation space. Let $\mathfrak{u} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$.

- (i) The Lower approximation of $\mathcal{X}$ with respect to $\mathcal{R}$ is denoted by $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$. That is, $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}) = \bigcup_{\mathfrak{r} \in \mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathfrak{r}) : \mathcal{R}(\mathfrak{r}) \subseteq \mathcal{X}}$, where $\mathcal{R}(\mathfrak{r})$ denotes the equivalence relation which contains $\mathfrak{r} \in \mathcal{U}$.
- (ii) The Upper approximation of $\mathcal{X}$ with respect to $\mathcal{R}$ is denoted by $\mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$. That is, $\mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}) = \bigcup_{\mathfrak{r} \in \mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathfrak{r}) : \mathcal{R}(\mathfrak{r}) \cap \mathcal{X} \neq \phi}$, where $\mathcal{R}(\mathfrak{r})$ denotes the equivalence relation which contains $\mathfrak{r} \in \mathcal{U}$.
- (iii) The Boundary region of $\mathcal{X}$ with respect to $\mathcal{R}$ is denoted by $\mathcal{B}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$. That is, $\mathcal{B}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}) = \mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}) - \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$.

Definition 2.2. [3] Let $\mathcal{U}$ be a universal set. $\mathcal{R}$ be an equivalence relation on $\mathcal{U}$, $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$ and $\tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}) = \{\mathcal{U}, \phi, \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), \mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), \mathcal{B}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})\}$ where $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$. $\tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$ satisfies the following axioms:

- (i) $\mathcal{U}$ and $\phi \in \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$.
- (ii) The union of elements of any subcollection of $\tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$ is in $\tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$.
- (iii) The intersection of the elements of any finite subcollection of $\tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$ is in $\tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$. Then $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ is called nano topological spaces. The members of $\tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$ are called nano open sets.

Definition 2.3. [6] Let $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ be a nano topological space. Then Kasaj topology is defined by $KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}) = \{(\mathfrak{K} \cap \mathfrak{S}) \cup (\mathfrak{K}' \cup \mathfrak{S}') : \mathfrak{K}, \mathfrak{K}' \in \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), \text{ fixed } \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{S}' \notin \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), \mathfrak{S} \cup \mathfrak{S}' = \mathcal{U}\}$. The Kasaj topology $KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$ satisfies the following conditions:

- (i) $\mathcal{U}, \phi \in KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$.
- (ii) The union of elements of any subcollection of $KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$ is in $KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$.
- (iii) The intersection of the elements of any finite sub collection of $KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$ is in $KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$.

Then $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ is called Kasaj topological spaces and the members of $KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$ are called Kasaj open sets(KS- $\mathfrak{D}$ sets) and the complement of a Kasaj open set is called a Kasaj-closed(KS- $\mathfrak{C}$) and the collection of all KS- $\mathfrak{C}$ set is denoted by $KSCL(\mathcal{X})$. The Kasaj closure and the Kasaj interior of a $\mathfrak{P}$ is denoted by $KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})$ and $KS_{int}(\mathfrak{P})$ respectively. It is defined by $KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \bigcap \{\mathfrak{Q} : \mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{Q}, \mathfrak{Q} \text{ is KS-}\mathfrak{C}\}$ and $KS_{int}(\mathfrak{P}) = \bigcup \{\mathfrak{Q} : \mathfrak{Q} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}, \mathfrak{Q} \text{ is KS-}\mathfrak{D}\}$.

Definition 2.4. [6] For any two subsets $\mathfrak{P}, \mathfrak{Q}$ of $\mathcal{U}$ in a Kasaj topological space $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$

- (i) $\mathfrak{P}$ is a KS- $\mathfrak{C}$ set iff $KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$.
- (ii) $\mathfrak{P}$ is a KS- $\mathfrak{D}$ set iff $KS_{int}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$.
- (iii) If $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{Q}$, then $KS_{int}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{int}(\mathfrak{Q})$ and $KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{Q})$.

- (iv) $KS_{cl}(KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})) = KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})$ and $KS_{int}(KS_{int}(\mathfrak{P})) = KS_{int}(\mathfrak{P})$.
- (v) $KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) \cup KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P} \cup \mathfrak{Q})$.
- (vi) $KS_{int}(\mathfrak{P}) \cup KS_{int}(\mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{int}(\mathfrak{P} \cup \mathfrak{Q})$.
- (vii) $KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{Q})$.
- (viii) $KS_{int}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{int}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{int}(\mathfrak{Q})$.
- (ix) $KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = [KS\text{-int}(\mathfrak{P})]^c$.
- (x) $KS_{int}(\mathfrak{P}) = [KS\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{P})]^c$.

Definition 2.5. A subset $\mathfrak{P}$ of $\mathcal{U}$ in $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ in Kasaj topological spaces and let $u \in \mathcal{U}$. A subset $\mathfrak{P}$ of $\mathcal{U}$ is said to be a KS-semi neighbourhood of u iff there exists a KS-semi open set $\mathcal{G}$ such that $u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$.

3. KS_{fgp} -Closed Sets and KS_{fgsp} -Closed Sets

In this section $KS_{fgp}\text{-}\mathcal{C}$ sets and $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathcal{C}$ sets in $\mathfrak{K.T.S}$ are developed and investigated.

Definition 3.1. If $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$ in $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ is said to be

- (i) KS- $\mathfrak{F}$ - $\mathcal{C}$ set, if $KS_{sint}(KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$.
- (ii) KS- $\mathfrak{F}$ - $\mathcal{S}$ - $\mathcal{C}$ set, if $KS_{sint}(KS_{scl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$.
- (iii) KS- $\mathfrak{F}$ - $\mathfrak{P}$ - $\mathcal{C}$ set, $KS_{sint}(KS_{pcl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$.
- (iv) KS- α - $\mathcal{C}$ set, if $KS_{sint}(KS_{\alpha cl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$.
- (v) KS- β - $\mathcal{C}$ set, if $KS_{sint}(KS_{\beta cl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$.

Example 3.2. Allow $\mathcal{U} = \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}$, with $\mathcal{U} \setminus \mathcal{R} = \{\{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{I}\}, \{\mathfrak{N}, e\}, \{\emptyset\}\}$ and $\mathcal{X} = \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{x}\}$. Again the nano topology, $\tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}) = \{U, \phi, \{\emptyset\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{I}\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{I}\}\}$. $\mathcal{S} = \{\mathfrak{x}\}$, $\mathcal{S}' = \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}$. Then $KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$ -open subsets are $U, \phi, \{\emptyset\}, \{\mathfrak{x}\}, \{\mathfrak{I}\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{x}\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{I}\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{I}\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{I}\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}$ and $KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$ - $\mathcal{C}$ subsets are $U, \phi, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}\}$. Then:

- (i) KS- $\mathfrak{F}$ - $\mathcal{C}$ subsets are $U, \phi, \{\mathfrak{x}\}, \{\mathfrak{N}\}, \{F\}, \{\mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}$.
- (ii) KS- $\mathfrak{F}$ - $\mathcal{S}$ - $\mathcal{C}$ subsets are $U, \phi, \{\emptyset\}, \{\mathfrak{x}\}, \{\mathfrak{N}\}, \{\mathfrak{I}\}, \{F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{x}\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{N}\}, \{\emptyset, F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{I}\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}\}, \{\mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{I}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{x}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}$.
- (iii) KS- $\mathfrak{F}$ - $\mathfrak{P}$ - $\mathcal{C}$ subsets are $U, \phi, \{\mathfrak{x}\}, \{\mathfrak{N}\}, \{F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}$.
- (iv) KS- $\mathfrak{F}$ - α - $\mathcal{C}$ subsets are $U, \phi, \{\mathfrak{x}\}, \{\mathfrak{N}\}, \{F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}$.
- (v) KS- $\mathfrak{F}$ - β - $\mathcal{C}$ subsets are $U, \phi, \{\emptyset\}, \{\mathfrak{x}\}, \{\mathfrak{N}\}, \{\mathfrak{I}\}, \{F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{x}\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{N}\}, \{\emptyset, F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{I}\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}\}, \{\mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{I}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{x}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}, \{\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{N}, \mathfrak{I}, F\}$.

Definition 3.3. If $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$ in $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ is said to be

- (vi) KS- $\mathfrak{F}$ - $\mathcal{S}$ - $\mathcal{C}$ set, if $KS_{fcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$ whenever $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$ and $\mathfrak{W}$ is KS- $\mathfrak{F}$ - $\mathcal{D}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$.
- (vii) KS- $\mathfrak{F}$ - $\mathcal{S}$ - $\mathfrak{P}$ - $\mathcal{C}$ set, if $KS_{fpcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$ whenever $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$ and $\mathfrak{W}$ is KS- $\mathfrak{F}$ - $\mathfrak{P}$ - $\mathcal{D}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$.

(viii) $KS_{\mathfrak{F}.\mathfrak{G}.S.\mathfrak{P}.C}$ set, if $KS_{f_{spcl}}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{Y}$ whenever $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{Y}$ and $\mathfrak{Y}$ is $KS_{\mathfrak{F}.S.\mathfrak{P}.D}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$.

The complement of $KS_{fg-C}[KS_{fgp-C}, KS_{fgsp-C}]$ sets are $KS_{fg-D}[KS_{fgp-D}, KS_{fgsp-D}]$ set in $\mathcal{U}$.

Example 3.4. Allow $\mathcal{U} = \{\emptyset, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, F\}$, with $\mathcal{U} \setminus \mathcal{R} = \{\{\emptyset, \alpha\}, \{\beta, \gamma\}, \{F\}\}$ and $\mathcal{X} = \{\emptyset, \alpha, \beta\}$. Again the nano topology, $\tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}) = \{U, \phi, \{\emptyset, \alpha\}, \{\emptyset, \alpha, \beta, \gamma\}, \{\beta, \gamma\}\}$. $\mathfrak{S} = \{\emptyset\}$, $\mathfrak{S}' = \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, F\}$. Then $KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$ -open subsets are $U, \phi, \{\emptyset\}, \{\alpha\}, \{\emptyset, \alpha\}, \{\beta, \gamma\}, \{\emptyset, \beta, \gamma\}, \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma\}, \{\emptyset, \alpha, \beta, \gamma\}, \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, F\}$ and $KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$ - $\mathfrak{C}$ subsets are $U, \phi, \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, F\}, \{\emptyset, \beta, \gamma, F\}, \{\emptyset, \alpha, \gamma, F\}, \{\alpha, \gamma, F\}, \{\beta, \gamma, F\}, \{\emptyset, \gamma, F\}, \{\gamma, F\}, \{\emptyset\}$. Then:

- (i) $KS_{\mathfrak{F}.S.C}$ subsets are: $U, \phi, \{\emptyset\}, \{F\}, \{\emptyset, F\}, \{\alpha, F\}, \{\beta, F\}, \{\gamma, F\}, \{\emptyset, \alpha, F\}, \{\emptyset, \beta, F\}, \{\emptyset, \gamma, F\}, \{\alpha, \beta, F\}, \{\alpha, \gamma, F\}, \{\beta, \gamma, F\}, \{\emptyset, \alpha, \beta, F\}, \{\emptyset, \alpha, \gamma, F\}, \{\emptyset, \beta, \gamma, F\}, \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, F\}$.
- (ii) $KS_{\mathfrak{F}.S.P.C}$ subsets are: $U, \phi, \{\emptyset\}, \{\alpha\}, \{\beta\}, \{\gamma\}, \{F\}, \{\emptyset, \beta\}, \{\emptyset, \gamma\}, \{\emptyset, F\}, \{\alpha, \beta\}, \{\alpha, \gamma\}, \{\beta, \gamma\}, \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma\}, \{\emptyset, \alpha, \beta\}, \{\emptyset, \alpha, \gamma\}, \{\emptyset, \beta, \gamma\}, \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma\}, \{\emptyset, \alpha, \beta, \gamma\}, \{\emptyset, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, F\}, \{\emptyset, \beta, \gamma, F\}, \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, F\}$.
- (iii) $KS_{\mathfrak{F}.S.S.P.C}$ subsets are: $U, \phi, \{\emptyset\}, \{\alpha\}, \{\beta\}, \{\gamma\}, \{F\}, \{\emptyset, \alpha\}, \{\emptyset, \beta\}, \{\emptyset, \gamma\}, \{\emptyset, F\}, \{\alpha, \beta\}, \{\alpha, \gamma\}, \{\alpha, F\}, \{\beta, \gamma\}, \{\beta, F\}, \{\gamma, F\}, \{\emptyset, \alpha, \beta\}, \{\emptyset, \alpha, \gamma\}, \{\emptyset, \alpha, F\}, \{\emptyset, \beta, \gamma\}, \{\emptyset, \beta, F\}, \{\emptyset, \gamma, F\}, \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma\}, \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, F\}, \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, F\}, \{\beta, \gamma, F\}, \{\alpha, \gamma, F\}, \{\beta, \gamma, F\}, \{\emptyset, \alpha, \beta, \gamma\}, \{\emptyset, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, F\}, \{\emptyset, \beta, \gamma, F\}, \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, F\}$.

Definition 3.5. If $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$ in $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ is said to be

- (i) Intersection of all $KS_{\mathfrak{F}.S.C}[KS_{\mathfrak{F}.S.P.C}, KS_{\mathfrak{F}.S.S.P.C}]$ sets containing $\mathfrak{P}$ is KS -feebly generalized closure[KS -feebly generalized pre closure, KS -feebly generalized semi pre closure] of $\mathfrak{P}$ and it is denoted by $KS_{fg-cl}(\mathfrak{P})[KS_{fgp-cl}(\mathfrak{P}), KS_{fgsp-cl}(\mathfrak{P})]$.
- (ii) Union of all $KS_{\mathfrak{F}.S.D}[KS_{\mathfrak{F}.S.P.D}, KS_{\mathfrak{F}.S.S.P.D}]$ sets contained in the set $\mathfrak{P}$ is the KS -feebly generalized interior[KS -feebly generalized pre interior, KS -feebly generalized semi pre interior] of $\mathfrak{P}$ and it is denoted by $KS_{fg-i}(\mathfrak{P})[KS_{fgp-i}(\mathfrak{P}), KS_{fgsp-i}(\mathfrak{P})]$.

Definition 3.6. If $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$ in $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ in $\mathfrak{K}.T.S$ and let $u \in \mathcal{U}$. A subset $\mathfrak{P}$ of $\mathcal{U}$ is called a $KS_{fg-N.B.D}[KS_{fgp-N.B.D}, KS_{fgsp-N.B.D}]$ of u iff there exists a $KS_{\mathfrak{F}.S.D}[KS_{\mathfrak{F}.S.P.D}, KS_{\mathfrak{F}.S.S.P.D}]$ set $\mathcal{G}$ such that $u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$.

Lemma 3.7. If $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$ in $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ in $\mathfrak{K}.T.S$. Then

- (i) $KS_{sint}(KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
- (ii) $KS_{sint}(KS_{scl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
- (iii) $KS_{sint}(KS_{pcl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})$
- (iv) $KS_{sint}(KS_{\alpha cl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
- (v) $KS_{sint}(KS_{\beta cl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
- (vi) $KS_{sint}(KS_{fgcl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
- (vii) $KS_{sint}(KS_{fgpcl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
- (viii) $KS_{sint}(KS_{fgspcl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})$.

Proof. (i) Let $u \in KS_{sint}(KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}))$.
 $\Leftrightarrow \cup\{\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{G} \text{ is } KS\text{-semi open, } \mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})\}$.
 $\Leftrightarrow KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})$ is KS -semi neighbourhood of u .
 $\Leftrightarrow$ there exists an KS -semi-open set $\mathcal{G}$ such that $u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
 $\Leftrightarrow u \in KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})$.

- (ii) Let $u \in KS_{sint}(KS_{scl}(\mathfrak{P}))$.
 $\Leftrightarrow \cup\{\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{G} \text{ is KS-semi open, } \mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{scl}(\mathfrak{P})\}$.
 $\Leftrightarrow KS_{scl}(\mathfrak{P})$ is KS-semi neighbourhood of u .
 $\Leftrightarrow$ there exists an KS-semi-open set $\mathcal{G}$ such that $u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{scl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
 $\Leftrightarrow u \in KS_{scl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
- (iii) Let $u \in KS_{sint}(KS_{pcl}(\mathfrak{P}))$.
 $\Leftrightarrow \cup\{\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{G} \text{ is KS-semi open, } \mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{pcl}(\mathfrak{P})\}$.
 $\Leftrightarrow KS_{pcl}(\mathfrak{P})$ is KS-semi neighbourhood of u .
 $\Leftrightarrow$ there exists an KS-semi-open set $\mathcal{G}$ such that $u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{pcl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
 $\Leftrightarrow u \in KS_{pcl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
- (iv) Let $u \in KS_{sint}(KS_{\alpha cl}(\mathfrak{P}))$.
 $\Leftrightarrow \cup\{\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{G} \text{ is KS-semi open, } \mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{\alpha cl}(\mathfrak{P})\}$.
 $\Leftrightarrow KS_{\alpha cl}(\mathfrak{P})$ is KS-semi neighbourhood of u .
 $\Leftrightarrow$ there exists an KS-semi-open set $\mathcal{G}$ such that $u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{\alpha cl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
 $\Leftrightarrow u \in KS_{\alpha cl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
- (v) Let $u \in KS_{sint}(KS_{\beta cl}(\mathfrak{P}))$.
 $\Leftrightarrow \cup\{\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{G} \text{ is KS-semi open, } \mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{\beta cl}(\mathfrak{P})\}$.
 $\Leftrightarrow KS_{\beta cl}(\mathfrak{P})$ is KS-semi neighbourhood of u .
 $\Leftrightarrow$ there exists an KS-semi-open set $\mathcal{G}$ such that $u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{\beta cl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
 $\Leftrightarrow u \in KS_{\beta cl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
- (vi) Let $u \in KS_{fcl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
 $\Leftrightarrow \cap\{\mathcal{F} : \mathcal{F} \text{ is KS-}\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathcal{C} \text{ and } \mathcal{F} \supseteq \mathfrak{P}\}$.
 $\Leftrightarrow KS_{fcl}(\mathfrak{P})$ is KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathcal{C}$ set, since it is intersection of KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathcal{C}$ set.
 $\Leftrightarrow KS_{fcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$.
 $\Leftrightarrow \mathcal{F}$ is any KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathcal{C}$ set containig $\mathfrak{P}$, then $KS_{fcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathcal{F}$.
 $\Leftrightarrow KS_{fcl}(\mathfrak{P})$ is the smallest KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathcal{C}$ set containing $\mathfrak{P}$, by Lemma 3.7(i).
 $\Leftrightarrow u \in KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
- (vii) Let $u \in KS_{fpcl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
 $\Leftrightarrow \cap\{\mathcal{F} : \mathcal{F} \text{ is KS-}\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathcal{C} \text{ and } \mathcal{F} \supseteq \mathfrak{P}\}$.
 $\Leftrightarrow KS_{fpcl}(\mathfrak{P})$ is KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathcal{C}$ set, since it is intersection of KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathcal{C}$ set.
 $\Leftrightarrow KS_{fpcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$.
 $\Leftrightarrow \mathcal{F}$ is any KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathcal{C}$ set containig $\mathfrak{P}$, then $KS_{fpcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathcal{F}$.
 $\Leftrightarrow KS_{fpcl}(\mathfrak{P})$ is the smallest KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathcal{C}$ set containing $\mathfrak{P}$, by Lemma 3.7 (ii).
 $\Leftrightarrow u \in KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})$.
- (viii) Let $u \in KS_{fspcl}(P)$.
 $\Leftrightarrow \cap\{\mathcal{F} : \mathcal{F} \text{ is KS-}\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{S}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathcal{C} \text{ and } \mathcal{F} \supseteq \mathfrak{P}\}$.
 $\Leftrightarrow KS_{fspcl}(\mathfrak{P})$ is KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{S}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathcal{C}$ set, since it is intersection of KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{S}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathcal{C}$ set.
 $\Leftrightarrow KS_{fspcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$.
 $\Leftrightarrow \mathcal{F}$ is any KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{S}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathcal{C}$ set containing $\mathfrak{P}$, then $KS_{fspcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathcal{F}$.
 $\Leftrightarrow KS_{fspcl}(\mathfrak{P})$ is the smallest KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{S}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathcal{C}$ set containing $\mathfrak{P}$, by Lemma 3.7 (iii).
 $\Leftrightarrow u \in KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})$.

□

Lemma 3.8. Let $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$ in $\mathfrak{K}\cdot\mathfrak{T}\cdot\mathfrak{S}$. Then $KS_{fpcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{pcl}(\mathfrak{P})$.

Proof. Let $u \in KS_{fpcl}(\mathfrak{P})$.

$\Leftrightarrow \cap\{\mathcal{F} : \mathcal{F} \text{ is KS-}\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathfrak{C} \text{ and } \mathcal{F} \supseteq \mathfrak{P}\}$.

$\Leftrightarrow KS_{fpcl}(\mathfrak{P})$ is KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathfrak{C}$ set, since it is intersection of KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathfrak{C}$ set.

$\Leftrightarrow KS_{fpcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$.

$\Leftrightarrow \mathcal{F}$ is any KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathfrak{C}$ set containing $\mathfrak{P}$, then $KS_{fpcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathcal{F}$.

$\Leftrightarrow KS_{fpcl}(\mathfrak{P})$ is the smallest KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathfrak{C}$ set containing $\mathfrak{P}$.

$\Leftrightarrow u \in KS_{pcl}(\mathfrak{P})$. □

Lemma 3.9. Let $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$ in $\mathfrak{K}\cdot\mathfrak{T}\cdot\mathfrak{S}$. Then $KS_{fspcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{spcl}(\mathfrak{P})$.

Proof. Let $u \in KS_{fspcl}(\mathfrak{P})$.

$\Leftrightarrow \cap\{\mathcal{F} : \mathcal{F} \text{ is KS-}\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{S}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathfrak{C} \text{ and } \mathcal{F} \supseteq \mathfrak{P}\}$.

$\Leftrightarrow KS_{fspcl}(\mathfrak{P})$ is KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{S}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathfrak{C}$ set, since it is intersection of KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{S}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathfrak{C}$ set.

$\Leftrightarrow KS_{fspcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$.

$\Leftrightarrow \mathcal{F}$ is any KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{S}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathfrak{C}$ set containing $\mathfrak{P}$, then $KS_{fspcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathcal{F}$.

$\Leftrightarrow KS_{fspcl}(\mathfrak{P})$ is the smallest KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{S}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathfrak{C}$ containing $\mathfrak{P}$.

$\Leftrightarrow u \in KS_{spcl}(\mathfrak{P})$. □

Theorem 3.10. About any combination of $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ in $\mathfrak{K}\cdot\mathfrak{T}\cdot\mathfrak{S}$, the subsequent propositions are true:

- (i) Every KS- $\mathfrak{C}$ set is KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{C}$.
- (ii) Every KS- $\mathfrak{C}$ set is KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{S}\cdot\mathfrak{C}$.
- (iii) Every KS- $\mathfrak{C}$ set is KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathfrak{C}$.
- (iv) Every KS- $\mathfrak{C}$ set is KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\alpha\cdot\mathfrak{C}$.
- (v) Every KS- $\mathfrak{C}$ set is KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\beta\cdot\mathfrak{C}$.
- (vi) Every KS- $\mathfrak{C}$ set is $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathfrak{C}$.
- (vii) Every KS- $\mathfrak{C}$ set is $KS_{fgp}\text{-}\mathfrak{C}$.
- (viii) Every KS- $\mathfrak{C}$ set is $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{C}$.
- (ix) Every KS-g $\mathfrak{C}$ set is $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathfrak{C}$.
- (x) Every KS-gp $\mathfrak{C}$ set is $KS_{fgp}\text{-}\mathfrak{C}$.
- (xi) Every KS-gsp $\mathfrak{C}$ set is $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{C}$.

Proof. (i) Suppose $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$, where $\mathfrak{P}$ is a KS- $\mathfrak{C}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$. Suddenly $KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$. Since by Lemma 3.7(i), $KS_{sint}(KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$. That is $KS_{sint}(KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$. Consequently $\mathfrak{P}$ is KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{C}$ set.

(ii) Suppose $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$, where $\mathfrak{P}$ is a KS- $\mathfrak{C}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$. Suddenly $KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$. Since by Lemma 3.7(ii), $KS_{sint}(KS_{scl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$. That is $KS_{sint}(KS_{scl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$. Consequently $\mathfrak{P}$ is KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{S}\cdot\mathfrak{C}$ set.

(iii) Suppose $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$, where $\mathfrak{P}$ is a KS- $\mathfrak{C}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$. Suddenly $KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$. Since by Lemma 3.7(iii), $KS_{sint}(KS_{pcl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$. That is $KS_{sint}(KS_{pcl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$. Consequently $\mathfrak{P}$ is KS- $\mathfrak{F}\cdot\mathfrak{P}\cdot\mathfrak{C}$.

- (iv) Suppose $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$, where $\mathfrak{P}$ is a KS- $\mathcal{C}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$. Suddenly $KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$. Since by Lemma 3.7(iv), $KS_{sint}(KS_{\alpha cl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$. That is $KS_{sint}(KS_{\alpha cl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$. Consequently $\mathfrak{P}$ is KS- $\mathfrak{F}.\alpha.\mathcal{C}$. set.
- (v) Suppose $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$, where $\mathfrak{P}$ is a KS- $\mathcal{C}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$. Suddenly $KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$. Since by Lemma 3.7(v), $KS_{sint}(KS_{\beta cl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$. That is $KS_{sint}(KS_{\beta cl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$. Consequently $\mathfrak{P}$ is KS- $\mathfrak{F}.\beta.\mathcal{C}$. set.
- (vi) Suppose $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, where $\mathfrak{P}$ is a KS- $\mathcal{C}$ set in $\mathcal{V}$. If $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$ and $\mathfrak{W}$ is a KS- $\mathfrak{F}.\mathcal{D}$ in $\mathcal{U}$. Already $\mathfrak{P}$ is KS- $\mathcal{C}$ set, $KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$. Already by Lemma 3.7(vi), $KS_{fcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$. Accordingly $KS_{fcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$. Consequently $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{fg}\mathcal{C}$ set.
- (vii) Suppose $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, where $\mathfrak{P}$ is a KS- $\mathcal{C}$ set in $\mathcal{V}$. If $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$ and $\mathfrak{W}$ is a KS- $\mathfrak{F}.\mathfrak{P}.\mathcal{D}$ in $\mathcal{U}$. Already $\mathfrak{P}$ is KS- $\mathcal{C}$ set, $KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$. Already by Lemma 3.7(vii) $KS_{fpcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$. Accordingly $KS_{fpcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$. Consequently $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{fgp}\mathcal{C}$ set.
- (viii) Suppose $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, where $\mathfrak{P}$ is a KS- $\mathcal{C}$ set in $\mathcal{V}$. If $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$ and $\mathfrak{W}$ is a KS- $\mathfrak{F}.\mathcal{S}.\mathfrak{P}.\mathcal{D}$ in $\mathcal{U}$. Already $\mathfrak{P}$ is KS- $\mathcal{C}$ set, $KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$. Already by Lemma 3.7(viii) $KS_{fspcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$. Accordingly $KS_{fspcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$. Consequently $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{fgsp}\mathcal{C}$ set.
- (ix) Suppose $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$, where $\mathfrak{P}$ is a KS- $\mathcal{C}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$. If $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$ and $\mathfrak{W}$ is a KS- $\mathcal{D}$ in $\mathcal{U}$. Already $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_g\mathcal{C}$ set, $KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$. Already by Lemma 3.7(i), $KS_{fcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$. Accordingly $KS_{fcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$. Consequently $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{fg}\mathcal{C}$ set.
- (x) Suppose $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$, where $\mathfrak{P}$ is a $KS_{gp}\mathcal{C}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$. If $\mathfrak{P}$ is a $KS_{gp}\mathcal{C}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$. If $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$ and $\mathfrak{W}$ is a KS- $\mathcal{D}$ in $\mathcal{U}$. Already $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{gp}\mathcal{C}$ set, $KS_{pcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$. Already by Lemma 3.8, $KS_{fpcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{pcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$. Accordingly $KS_{fpcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$. Consequently $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{fgp}\mathcal{C}$ set.
- (xi) Suppose $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$, where $\mathfrak{P}$ is a $KS_{gsp}\mathcal{C}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$. If $\mathfrak{P}$ is a $KS_{gsp}\mathcal{C}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$. If $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$ and $\mathfrak{W}$ is a KS- $\mathcal{D}$ in $\mathcal{U}$. Already $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{gsp}\mathcal{C}$ set, $KS_{spcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$. Already by Lemma 3.9, $KS_{fspcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{spcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$. Accordingly $KS_{fspcl}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{W}$. Consequently $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{fgsp}\mathcal{C}$ set.

□

The opposite of the aforementioned claims need not be true, as shown by the example that follows.

Example 3.11. Allow $\mathcal{U} = \{\vartheta, \varkappa, \aleph, \beth, F\}$, with $\mathcal{U} \setminus \mathcal{R} = \{\{\beth, F\}, \{\vartheta, \varkappa\}, \{\aleph\}\}$ and $\mathcal{X} = \{\vartheta, \aleph\}$. Again the nano topology, $\tau_R(\mathcal{X}) = \{\mathcal{U}, \phi, \{\aleph\}, \{\vartheta, \varkappa, \aleph\}, \{\vartheta, \varkappa\}\}$. $\mathcal{S} = \{\vartheta\}$, $\mathcal{S}' = \{\varkappa, \aleph, \beth, F\}$. Then: $KS_R(\mathcal{X})$ -open subsets are $\mathcal{U}, \phi, \{\vartheta\}, \{\varkappa\}, \{\aleph\}, \{\vartheta, \aleph\}, \{\vartheta, \varkappa\}, \{\varkappa, \aleph\}, \{\vartheta, \varkappa, \aleph\}, \{\varkappa, \aleph, \beth, F\}$ and $KS_R(\mathcal{X})$ - $\mathcal{C}$ subsets are $\mathcal{U}, \phi, \{\varkappa, \aleph, \beth, F\}, \{\vartheta, \aleph, \beth, F\}, \{\vartheta, \varkappa, \beth, F\}, \{\varkappa, \beth, F\}, \{\aleph, \beth, F\}, \{\vartheta, \beth, F\}, \{\beth, F\}, \{\vartheta\}$. Then:

- (i) KS- $\mathfrak{F}.\mathcal{C}$ subsets are $\mathcal{U}, \phi, \{\vartheta\}, \{\beth\}, \{F\}, \{\vartheta, \beth\}, \{\vartheta, F\}, \{\beth, F\}, \{\vartheta, \beth, F\}, \{\varkappa, \beth, F\}, \{\aleph, \beth, F\}, \{\vartheta, \varkappa, \beth, F\}, \{\vartheta, \aleph, \beth, F\}, \{\varkappa, \aleph, \beth, F\}$.
- (ii) KS- $\mathfrak{F}.\mathcal{S}.\mathcal{C}$ subsets are $\mathcal{U}, \phi, \{\vartheta\}, \{\varkappa\}, \{\aleph\}, \{\beth\}, \{F\}, \{\vartheta, \varkappa\}, \{\vartheta, \aleph\}, \{\vartheta, \beth\}, \{\vartheta, F\}, \{\varkappa, \beth\}, \{\varkappa, F\}, \{\aleph, \beth\}, \{\aleph, F\}, \{\beth, F\}, \{\vartheta, \varkappa, \beth\}, \{\vartheta, \varkappa, F\}, \{\vartheta, \aleph, \beth\}, \{\vartheta, \aleph, F\}, \{\vartheta, \beth, F\}, \{\varkappa, \beth, F\}, \{\aleph, \beth, F\}, \{\vartheta, \varkappa, \beth, F\}, \{\vartheta, \aleph, \beth, F\}, \{\varkappa, \aleph, \beth, F\}$.
- (iii) KS- $\mathfrak{F}.\mathfrak{P}.\mathcal{C}$ subsets are $\mathcal{U}, \phi, \{\vartheta\}, \{\beth\}, \{F\}, \{\vartheta, \beth\}, \{\vartheta, F\}, \{\beth, F\}, \{\vartheta, \beth, F\}, \{\varkappa, \beth, F\}, \{\aleph, \beth, F\}, \{\vartheta, \varkappa, \beth, F\}, \{\vartheta, \aleph, \beth, F\}, \{\varkappa, \aleph, \beth, F\}$.
- (iv) KS- $\mathfrak{F}.\alpha.\mathcal{C}$ subsets are $\mathcal{U}, \phi, \{\vartheta\}, \{\beth\}, \{F\}, \{\vartheta, \beth\}, \{\vartheta, F\}, \{\beth, F\}, \{\vartheta, \beth, F\}, \{\varkappa, \beth, F\}, \{\aleph, \beth, F\}, \{\vartheta, \varkappa, \beth, F\}, \{\vartheta, \aleph, \beth, F\}, \{\varkappa, \aleph, \beth, F\}$.

- (v) $KS_{\mathfrak{F},\beta}\mathcal{C}$ subsets are $\mathcal{U}, \phi, \{\emptyset\}, \{\mathcal{K}\}, \{\mathcal{N}\}, \{\mathcal{J}\}, \{F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{K}\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{N}\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{J}\}, \{\emptyset, F\}, \{\mathcal{K}, \mathcal{J}\}, \{\mathcal{K}, F\}, \{\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{J}\}, \{\mathcal{N}, F\}, \{\mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{K}, \mathcal{J}\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{K}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{N}, \mathcal{J}\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{N}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\mathcal{K}, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{K}, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{N}, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\mathcal{K}, \mathcal{N}, \mathcal{J}, F\}$.
- (vi) $KS_{fg}\mathcal{C}$ subsets are $\mathcal{U}, \phi, \{\emptyset\}, \{\mathcal{J}\}, \{F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{J}\}, \{\emptyset, F\}, \{\mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\mathcal{K}, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{K}, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{N}, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\mathcal{K}, \mathcal{N}, \mathcal{J}, F\}$.
- (vii) $KS_{fgp}\mathcal{C}$ subsets are $\mathcal{U}, \phi, \{\emptyset\}, \{\mathcal{J}\}, \{F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{J}\}, \{\emptyset, F\}, \{\mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\mathcal{K}, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{K}, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{N}, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\mathcal{K}, \mathcal{N}, \mathcal{J}, F\}$.
- (viii) $KS_{fgsp}\mathcal{C}$ subsets are $\mathcal{U}, \phi, \{\emptyset\}, \{\mathcal{K}\}, \{\mathcal{N}\}, \{\mathcal{J}\}, \{F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{K}\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{N}\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{J}\}, \{\emptyset, F\}, \{\mathcal{K}, \mathcal{J}\}, \{\mathcal{K}, F\}, \{\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{J}\}, \{\mathcal{N}, F\}, \{\mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{K}, \mathcal{J}\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{K}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{N}, \mathcal{J}\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{N}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\mathcal{K}, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{K}, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\emptyset, \mathcal{N}, \mathcal{J}, F\}, \{\mathcal{K}, \mathcal{N}, \mathcal{J}, F\}$.

Theorem 3.12. If $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{C}$ set iff $KS_{sint}(KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$.

Proof. Necessity: Suppose $KS_{sint}(KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$. Assume $KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{c}$. Again $KS_{sint}(\mathfrak{c}) \subseteq \mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathbb{C}$ and $\mathbb{C}$ is $KS\mathcal{C}$. Consequently, $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{C}$ set.

Sufficiency: If $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{C}$, then for some $KS\mathcal{C}$ set $\mathbb{C}$, $KS_{sint}(\mathfrak{c}) \subseteq \mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathbb{C}$. Already $\mathfrak{c} \subseteq KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})$ and so $KS_{sint}(\mathfrak{c}) \subseteq KS_{sint}(KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P}))$, because for any subset Ω of $\mathcal{U}$, $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \Omega$ this implies that $KS_{sint}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{sint}(\Omega)$. Consequently $KS_{sint}(KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq \mathbb{C} \subseteq KS_{sint}(\mathfrak{c}) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$. Accordingly $KS_{sint}(KS_{cl}(\mathfrak{P})) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$. $\square$

Theorem 3.13. If $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{C}$ and $KS_{sint}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \Omega \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$, suddenly Ω is $KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{C}$.

Proof. Since $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{C}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$. Suppose $\mathbb{C}$ be a $KS\mathcal{C}$ set in such a way that $KS_{sint}(\mathfrak{c}) \subseteq \mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathbb{C}$. Evidently, $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{C}$, because for any subset Ω of $\mathcal{U}$, $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \Omega$, this implies that $KS_{sint}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{sint}(\Omega)$ and $KS_{sint}(KS_{sint}(\mathfrak{P})) = KS_{sint}(\mathfrak{P})$, $KS_{sint}(\mathfrak{c}) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$, this implies that $KS_{sint}(KS_{sint}(\mathfrak{c})) \subseteq KS_{sint}(\mathfrak{P})$, this implies that $KS_{sint}(\mathfrak{c}) \subseteq KS_{sint}(\mathfrak{P})$. Consequently, $KS_{sint}(\mathfrak{c}) \subseteq \Omega \subseteq \mathbb{C}$. Hence Ω is $KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{C}$. $\square$

Theorem 3.14. Let $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$. For an element $u \in \mathcal{U}$, $u \in KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{C}$ set of $\mathfrak{P}$ iff $\mathfrak{D} \cup \mathfrak{P} \neq \phi$ for every $KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{C}$ set $\mathfrak{D}$ containing u .

Proof. Necessity: Let $u \in KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{C}(\mathfrak{P})$. Suppose there exists $KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{C}$ set $\mathfrak{D}$ containing u in such a way that $\mathfrak{D} \cup \mathfrak{P} = \phi$. Again $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{D}^u$. Since $\mathfrak{P}^u$ is $KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{C}$ containing $\mathfrak{P}$, we have $KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{C} \mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{D}^u$, this implies that $u \notin KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{C}(\mathfrak{P})$. This is a contradiction.

Sufficiency: Suppose that $u \in KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{C}(\mathfrak{P})$. Then by definition, there exists a $KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{C}$ set $\mathcal{U}$ containing $\mathfrak{P}$ such that $u \notin \mathfrak{F}$. Suddenly $u \in \mathfrak{F}^u$ and $\mathfrak{F}^u$ is $KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{D}$ set. Also $\mathfrak{F}^u \cap \mathcal{P} = \phi$, which is contrary to the hypothesis. Accordingly $u \in KS_{\mathfrak{F}}\mathcal{C}$ $\square$

Theorem 3.15. Let $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$. Then $KS_{fg}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) = \cup\{\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{G} \text{ is } KS_{fg}\text{-open, } \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}\}$.

Proof. Suppose $u \in KS_{fg}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$.

$\Leftrightarrow \mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{fg}\mathcal{N}\mathfrak{B}\mathcal{D}$ of u .

$\Leftrightarrow \exists KS_{fg}\text{-open set } \mathcal{G}, \ni u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$.

$\Leftrightarrow \mathfrak{P} \in \cup\{\mathcal{G} : \mathfrak{P} \text{ is } KS_{fg}\text{-open, } \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}\}$.

Hence $KS_{fg}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) = \cup\{\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{G} \text{ is } KS_{fg}\text{-open, } \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}\}$. $\square$

Theorem 3.16. Let $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ in $\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{I}\mathcal{S}$ and $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$. Then

- (i) $KS_{fg}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is a KS_{fg} -open set in $\mathcal{U}$.
- (ii) $KS_{fg}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is the biggest KS_{fg} -open set contained in $\mathfrak{P}$.
- (iii) $\mathfrak{P}$ is KS_{fg} -open iff $KS_{fg}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$.

Proof. (1) Let u be any arbitrary point of $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$. Then u is a KS-feebly generalized interior point of $\mathfrak{P}$. Hence by definition, $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathfrak{N.B.D}$ of u . Then there exists a KS_{fg} -open set $\mathcal{G}$ such that $u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$. Since $\mathcal{G}$ is KS_{fg} -open, it is $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathfrak{N.B.D}$ of each of its points and so $\mathfrak{P}$ is also a $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathfrak{N.B.D}$ of each point of $\mathcal{G}$. It follows that every point of $\mathcal{G}$ is a KS-feebly generalized interior point of $\mathfrak{P}$ so that $\mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$. Thus it is shown that to each $u \in KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$, there exists a KS-feebly generalized open set $\mathcal{G}$ such that $u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$. Hence $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is a $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathfrak{N.B.D}$ of each of its points and consequently $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is KS_{fg} -open set in $\mathcal{U}$.

(2) Let $\mathcal{G}$ be any subset of $\mathfrak{P}$ and let $u \in \mathfrak{P}$ so that $u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$. Since $\mathcal{G}$ is KS_{fg} -open, $\mathfrak{P}$ is a $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathfrak{N.B.D}$ of u and consequently u is a KS-feebly generalized interior point of $\mathfrak{P}$. Hence $u \in KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$. Thus we have shown that $u \in \mathcal{G} \Rightarrow u \in KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ and so $\mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$. Hence $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ contains every KS- $\mathfrak{F.G.D}$ subset of $\mathfrak{P}$ and it is therefore the biggest KS- $\mathfrak{F.G.D}$ subset of $\mathfrak{P}$.

(3) Let $\mathfrak{P} = KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$, by(1) $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is a KS_{fg} -open set and therefore $\mathfrak{P}$ is also KS_{fg} -open. Conversely $\mathfrak{P}$ be a KS_{fg} -open. Then $\mathfrak{P}$ is surely identical with the largest KS_{fg} -open subset of $\mathfrak{P}$. But by (2), $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is the biggest KS- $\mathfrak{F.G.D}$ subset of $\mathfrak{P}$. Hence $\mathfrak{P} = KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$. □

Theorem 3.17. For any two subsets $\mathfrak{P}$ and $\mathfrak{Q}$ of $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ in $\mathfrak{K.T.G}$.

- (i) If $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{Q}$, then $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$.
- (ii) $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q}) = KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$.
- (iii) $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cup KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cup \mathfrak{Q})$.
- (iv) $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathcal{U}) = \mathcal{U}$.
- (v) $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\phi) = \phi$.

Proof. (i) Let $\mathfrak{P}$ and $\mathfrak{Q}$ be subsets of $\mathcal{U}$ such that $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{Q}$. Let $u \in KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$. Then there exists a KS- $\mathfrak{F.G.D}$ set F such that $u \in F \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$ and hence $u \in KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$. Hence $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$.

(ii) We know that $\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$ and $\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q} \subseteq \mathfrak{Q}$. We have by 1) $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ and $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$. This implies that $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q}) \cap KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ ———(A).

Again, let $u \in KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$. Then $u \in KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ and $u \in KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$. Then there exists KS- $\mathfrak{F.G.D}$ sets F and H such that $u \in F \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$ and $u \in H \subseteq \mathfrak{Q}$. $F \cap H$ is a KS- $\mathfrak{F.G.D}$ set such that $u \in (F \cap H) \subseteq (\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q})$. Hence $u \in KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q})$. Thus $u \in KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$ implies that $u \in KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q})$. Therefore $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q})$ ———(B).

From (A) and (B), it follows that $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q}) = KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$.

The proofs of (iii),(iv),(v) are obvious. □

Theorem 3.18. Let $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ be a $\mathfrak{K.T.G}$ and let $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$. Then:

- (i) $KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) = (KS_{fg}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{P})^c)^c$.
- (ii) $KS_{fg}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{P}^c) = (KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}))^c$.
- (iii) $KS_{fg}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = (KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}))^c$.

Proof. (i) Obvious.

(ii) Taking complements in (1), $(KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}))^c = (KS_{fg}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{P}^c))^c = KS_{fg}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{P}^c)$. Taking complements again, $(KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}))^c = (KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}^c))^c$. Since $(S^c)^c = S$ for any set S .

(iii) By (2) $KS_{fg}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{P}^c) = (KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}))^c$. Replacing $\mathfrak{P}$ by $\mathfrak{P}^c$ in this, we get $KS_{fg}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{P}^c)^c = (KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}^c))^c = (KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}^c))^c$. Hence $KS_{fg}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = (KS_{fg}\text{-}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}^c))^c$. □

Theorem 3.19. Let $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$. Then $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) = \cup\{\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{G} \text{ is } KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-open, } \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}\}$.

Proof. Suppose $u \in KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$.

$\Leftrightarrow \mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{N.B.D}$ of u .

$\Leftrightarrow \exists KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-open set } \mathcal{G}, \ni u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$.

$\Leftrightarrow \mathfrak{P} \in \cup\{\mathcal{G} : \mathfrak{P} \text{ is } KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-open, } \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}\}$.

Hence $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) = \cup\{\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{G} \text{ is } KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-open, } \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}\}$. □

Theorem 3.20. Let $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ in $\mathfrak{K.T.S}$ and $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$. Then:

- (i) $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is a $KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-open}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$.
- (ii) $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is the biggest $KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-open}$ set contained in $\mathfrak{P}$.
- (iii) $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-open}$ iff $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$.

Proof. (1) Let u be any arbitrary point of $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$. Then u is a KS-feebly generalized pre interior point of $\mathfrak{P}$. Hence by definition, $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{N.B.D}$ of u . Then there exists a $KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-open}$ set $\mathcal{G}$ such that $u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$. Since $\mathcal{G}$ is $KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-open}$, it is $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{N.B.D}$ of each of its points and so $\mathfrak{P}$ is also a $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{N.B.D}$ of each point of $\mathcal{G}$. It follows that every point of $\mathcal{G}$ is a KS-feebly generalized pre interior point of $\mathfrak{P}$ so that $\mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$. Thus it is shown that to each $u \in KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$, there exists a KS-feebly generalized pre open set $\mathcal{G}$ such that $u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$. Hence $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is a $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{N.B.D}$ of each of its points and consequently $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is $KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-open}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$.

(2) Let $\mathcal{G}$ be any subset of $\mathfrak{P}$ and let $u \in \mathfrak{P}$ so that $u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$. Since $\mathcal{G}$ is $KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-open}$, $\mathfrak{P}$ is a $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{N.B.D}$ of u and consequently u is a KS-feebly generalized pre interior point of $\mathfrak{P}$. Hence $u \in KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$. Thus we have shown that $u \in \mathcal{G} \Rightarrow u \in KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ and so $\mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$. Hence $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ contains every $KS\text{-}\mathfrak{F.G.P.D}$ subset of $\mathfrak{P}$ and it is therefore the largest $KS\text{-}\mathfrak{F.G.P.D}$ subset of $\mathfrak{P}$.

(3) Let $\mathfrak{P} = KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$, by(1) $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is a $KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-open}$ set and therefore $\mathfrak{P}$ is also $KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-open}$. Conversely $\mathfrak{P}$ be a $KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-open}$. Then $\mathfrak{P}$ is surely identical with the largest $KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-open}$ subset of $\mathfrak{P}$. But by (2), $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is the biggest $KS\text{-}\mathfrak{F.G.P.D}$ subset of $\mathfrak{P}$. Hence $\mathfrak{P} = KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$. □

Theorem 3.21. For any two subsets $\mathfrak{P}$ and $\mathfrak{Q}$ of $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ in $\mathfrak{K.T.S}$.

- (i) If $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{Q}$, then $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$.
- (ii) $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q}) = KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$.
- (iii) $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cup KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cup \mathfrak{Q})$.
- (iv) $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathcal{U}) = \mathcal{U}$.
- (v) $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\phi) = \phi$.

Proof. (i) Let $\mathfrak{P}$ and $\mathfrak{Q}$ be subsets of $\mathcal{U}$ such that $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{Q}$. Let $u \in KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$. Then there exists a $KS\text{-}\mathfrak{F.G.P.D}$ set F such that $u \in F \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$ and hence $u \in KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$. Hence $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$.

(ii) We know that $\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$ and $\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q} \subseteq \mathfrak{Q}$. We have by 1) $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ and $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$. This implies that $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q}) \cap KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ —
 _____(A).

Again, let $u \in KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$. Then $u \in KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ and $u \in KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$. Then there exists $KS\text{-}\mathfrak{F.G.P.D}$ sets F and H such that $u \in F \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$ and $u \in H \subseteq \mathfrak{Q}$. $F \cap H$ is a $KS\text{-}\mathfrak{F.G.P.D}$ set such that $u \in (F \cap H) \subseteq (\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q})$. Hence $u \in KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q})$. Thus $u \in KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$

implies that $u \in KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q})$. Therefore $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q})$ ——(B). From (A) and (B), it follows that $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q}) = KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$. The proofs of (iii),(iv),(v) are obvious.

□

Theorem 3.22. Let $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ be a $\mathfrak{K.T.S}$ and let $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$. Then:

- (i) $KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) = (KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{P})^c)^c$.
- (ii) $KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{P}^c) = (KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}))^c$.
- (iii) $KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = (KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}))^c$.

Proof. (i) Obvious.

(ii) Taking complements in (1), $(KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}))^c = (KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{P}^c))^c = KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{P}^c)$. Taking complements again, $(KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}^c))^c = (KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}))^c$. Since $(S^c)^c = S$ for any set S.

(iii) By (2) $KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{P}^c) = (KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}))^c$. Replacing $\mathfrak{P}$ by $\mathfrak{P}^c$ in this, we get $KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{P}^c)^c = (KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}^c))^c = (KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}))^c$. Hence $KS_{f_{gp}}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{P}) = (KS_{f_{gp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}))^c$.

□

Theorem 3.23. Let $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$. Then: $KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) = \cup\{\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{G} \text{ is } KS_{f_{gsp}}\text{-open, } \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}\}$.

Proof. Suppose $u \in KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$.

$\Leftrightarrow \mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathfrak{N.B.D}$ of u .

$\Leftrightarrow \exists KS_{f_{gsp}}\text{-open set } \mathcal{G}, \ni u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$.

$\Leftrightarrow \mathfrak{P} \in \cup\{\mathcal{G} : \mathfrak{P} \text{ is } KS_{f_{gsp}}\text{-open, } \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}\}$.

Hence $KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) = \cup\{\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{G} \text{ is } KS_{f_{gsp}}\text{-open, } \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}\}$.

□

Theorem 3.24. Let $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ in $\mathfrak{K.T.S}$ and $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$. Then:

- (i) $KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is a $KS_{f_{gsp}}\text{-open}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$.
- (ii) $KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is the biggest $KS_{f_{gsp}}\text{-open}$ set contained in $\mathfrak{P}$.
- (iii) $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{f_{gsp}}\text{-open}$ iff $KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) = \mathfrak{P}$.

Proof. (1) Let u be any arbitrary point of $KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$. Then u is a KS-feeibly generalized semi pre interior point of $\mathfrak{P}$. Hence by definition, $\mathfrak{P}$ is $KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathfrak{N.B.D}$ of u . Then there exists a $KS_{f_{gsp}}\text{-open}$ set $\mathcal{G}$ such that $u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$. Since $\mathcal{G}$ is $KS_{f_{gsp}}\text{-open}$, it is $KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathfrak{N.B.D}$ of each of its points and so $\mathfrak{P}$ is also a $KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathfrak{N.B.D}$ of each point of $\mathcal{G}$. It follows that every point of $\mathcal{G}$ is a KS-feeibly generalized semi pre interior point of $\mathfrak{P}$ so that $\mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$. Thus it is shown that to each $u \in KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$, there exists a KS-feeibly generalized semi pre open set $\mathcal{G}$ such that $u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$. Hence $KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is a $KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathfrak{N.B.D}$ of each of its points and consequently $KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is $KS_{f_{gsp}}\text{-open}$ set in $\mathcal{U}$.

(2) Let $\mathcal{G}$ be any subset of $\mathfrak{P}$ and let $u \in \mathfrak{P}$ so that $u \in \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$. Since $\mathcal{G}$ is $KS_{f_{gsp}}\text{-open}$, $\mathfrak{P}$ is a $KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathfrak{N.B.D}$ of u and consequently u is a KS-feeibly generalized semi pre interior point of $\mathfrak{P}$. Hence $u \in KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$. Thus we have shown that $u \in \mathcal{G} \Rightarrow u \in KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ and so $\mathcal{G} \subseteq KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$. Hence $KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ contains every KS- $\mathfrak{F.G.S.P.D}$ subset of $\mathfrak{P}$ and it is therefore the biggest KS- $\mathfrak{F.G.S.P.D}$ subset of $\mathfrak{P}$.

(3) Let $\mathfrak{P} = KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$, by(1) $KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is a $KS_{f_{gsp}}\text{-open}$ set and therefore $\mathfrak{P}$ is also $KS_{f_{gsp}}\text{-open}$. Conversely $\mathfrak{P}$ be a $KS_{f_{gsp}}\text{-open}$. Then $\mathfrak{P}$ is surely identical with the largest $KS_{f_{gsp}}\text{-open}$ subset of $\mathfrak{P}$. But by (2), $KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ is the biggest KS- $\mathfrak{F.G.S.P.D}$ subset of $\mathfrak{P}$. Hence $\mathfrak{P} = KS_{f_{gsp}}\mathcal{I}(\mathfrak{P})$.

□

Theorem 3.25. For any two subsets $\mathfrak{P}$ and $\mathfrak{Q}$ of $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ in $\mathfrak{K.T.S}$.

- (i) If $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{Q}$, then $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$.
- (ii) $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q}) = KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$.
- (iii) $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cup KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cup \mathfrak{Q})$.
- (iv) $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathcal{U}) = \mathcal{U}$.
- (v) $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\phi) = \phi$.

Proof. (i) Let $\mathfrak{P}$ and $\mathfrak{Q}$ be subsets of $\mathcal{U}$ such that $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{Q}$. Let $u \in KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P})$. Then there exists a $\mathfrak{K.S.}\mathfrak{F.}\mathfrak{G.}\mathfrak{S.}\mathfrak{P.}\mathfrak{Q}$ set F such that $u \in F \subseteq \mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathfrak{Q}$ and hence $u \in KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$. Hence $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \subseteq KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$.

(ii) We know that $\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q} \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$ and $\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q} \subseteq \mathfrak{Q}$. We have by 1) $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ and $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$. This implies that $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$ (A).
 Again, let $u \in KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$. Then $u \in KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P})$ and $u \in KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$. Then there exists $\mathfrak{K.S.}\mathfrak{F.}\mathfrak{G.}\mathfrak{S.}\mathfrak{P.}\mathfrak{Q}$ sets F and H such that $u \in F \subseteq \mathfrak{P}$ and $u \in H \subseteq \mathfrak{Q}$. $F \cap H$ is a $\mathfrak{K.S.}\mathfrak{F.}\mathfrak{G.}\mathfrak{S.}\mathfrak{P.}\mathfrak{Q}$ set such that $u \in (F \cap H) \subseteq (\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q})$. Hence $u \in KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q})$. Thus $u \in KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$ implies that $u \in KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q})$. Therefore $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{Q}) \subseteq KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q})$ (B).
 From (A) and (B), it follows that $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P} \cap \mathfrak{Q}) = KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}) \cap KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{Q})$. The proofs of (iii),(iv),(v) are obvious. □

Theorem 3.26. Let $(\mathcal{U}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), KS_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ be a $\mathfrak{K.T.S}$ and let $\mathfrak{P} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$. Then:

- (i) $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}) = (KS_{fgsp}\text{-}cl(\mathfrak{P}))^c$.
- (ii) $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}cl(\mathfrak{P}^c) = (KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}))^c$.
- (iii) $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}cl(\mathfrak{P}) = (KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}^c))^c$.

Proof. (i) Obvious.
 (ii) Taking complements in (i), $(KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}))^c = (KS_{fgsp}\text{-}cl(\mathfrak{P}^c))^c = KS_{fgsp}\text{-}cl(\mathfrak{P}^c)$. Taking complements again, $(KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}^c))^c = (KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}))^c$. Since $(S^c)^c = S$ for any set S .
 (iii) By (ii) $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}cl(\mathfrak{P}^c) = (KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}))^c$. Replacing $\mathfrak{P}$ by $\mathfrak{P}^c$ in this, we get $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}cl(\mathfrak{P}^c)^c = (KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}^c))^c = (KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}))^c$. Hence $KS_{fgsp}\text{-}cl(\mathfrak{P}) = (KS_{fgsp}\text{-}\mathfrak{I}(\mathfrak{P}^c))^c$. □

4. Acknowledgment

The authors would like to thank the referees for their useful comments and suggestions.

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